

REVIEW ARTICLE

FEATURES OF TEACHING BASED ON THE 4K APPROACH IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article provides an analysis of innovative approaches in the educational environment in the context of globalization, as well as a pedagogical analysis of the content of the 4C approach components, collaboration, collaborative work, a methodology for regularly improving the experience of critical thinking based on teamwork, mutual pairing, the ability to apply it in various everyday situations using personal and academic experience, the ability to create creative solutions, the ability to choose the main ones and analyze them, information about the effectiveness of assimilation, practical details. Also, the prospects of applying modern pedagogical methods and technologies in the formation of these competencies are analyzed.

Keywords

collaboration, critical thinking, primary education, students, skill, assessment, approach, feedback in the team, globalization, modern education.

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In the 21st century, fundamental changes in the field of education, globalization, technological progress and increased information flow require not only knowledge, but also important competencies from a modern person. In this regard, the need to introduce a 4K approach in the education system is increasing. In particular, today, broad opportunities have been created for the development of general secondary education to higher education, a wide path has been opened for the development of education, science, culture, art, and the training of highly qualified specialists has begun to be brought closer to world standards.

Continuing education in our country is a continuous collaborative activity of skilled teachers and inquisitive learners, in which the development of the individual, his education and upbringing are also improved. In the lessons, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and qualifications to the students through exercises, and the students, as a result of mastering it, acquire the competence to use it independently. In the process of studying academic subjects in the educational process, students use various forms and means of mastering, that is, they rely on their own similarities in receiving, processing and applying the information being mastered. Also, the continuous cooperation of the teacher and students in the educational process in the form of independent work of

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students, in the classroom and extracurricular activities solves educational and educational problems.

Our main goal in reforming education is that we want to build a great state with a great future - New Uzbekistan. The future of our country is in the hands of today's growing, well-developed generations. We want the great future of Uzbekistan to be in the hands of highly spiritual, physically healthy, qualified and creative individuals. In order to develop individuals with such qualities, we must pay attention to the education system. For this purpose, the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System until 2030 sets the task of improving teaching methods.

Accordingly, certain work has been carried out to update textbooks. In particular, based on advanced foreign experience, textbooks for grades 1-4 have been newly prepared based on the "4K" model. The use of the "4K" model has passed many tests and, importantly, has been thoroughly enriched based on modern approaches. This development strategy is aimed at the comprehensive development of children as a methodological approach aimed at the formation of key competencies in modern education and includes 4 key competencies. In particular

Creativity – creativity, putting forward new ideas, solving problems in an unusual way. In this case, in modern society, every student, and indeed humanity, is expected to think in new ways, put forward ideas, and solve problems with original solutions. The use of project work and design thinking technologies in education is more effective in forming this competency.

Critical Thinking – means analyzing, deeply understanding problems, and drawing conclusions based on evidence. In this approach, critical thinking helps the student to approach events independently and draw conclusions based on evidence, and this skill is also of particular importance in the development of media culture.

Communication – conveying one's thoughts clearly and understandably and communicating effectively. That is, effective communication, expressing thoughts clearly and understanding the audience are important criteria in today's globalized world. In particular, it is necessary to pay increased attention to the study of foreign languages and speech activities.

Collaboration is teamwork, collaborative decision-making, and the skills of sharing responsibility in a team and working with people from different cultures are considered relevant in an integrated environment. In this regard, multi-form group work is considered effective.

Elementary school students are naturally creative. Activities such as games, energizers, storytelling, drawing, and puppet shows are essential to developing this ability. Through creativity, students learn to express themselves freely and make independent decisions. Not only do they develop the skills to express themselves, listen to others, and come up with creative solutions, they also develop independent thinking, teamwork, flexibility, and emotional stability.

In addition, from an early age, the foundation for life readiness, career choice, and communication skills is laid. Of course, such work is carried out based on the ways of implementing the 4K approach in education:

Active learning methods (discussion, debate, brainstorming, cluster, concept maps, assessments).

- Organization of interdisciplinary projects through the STEAM approach.

- Use of digital technologies (interactive platforms, artificial intelligence, virtual experiences).
- Modern forms of assessment (rubrics, portfolios, peer assessment, learning platforms).

According to our research, the importance of this approach in the context of globalization requires mutual integration, the speed of information flow, close contacts with different cultures and languages. Therefore, while communication skills are of particular importance, creativity and innovative thinking are necessary for children to be competitive in the rapidly changing world. Critical thinking is essential for assessing the reliability of information coming from different sources, and collaborative relationships are the basis for successful work in group projects and distance learning.

Education focuses on teaching the student to think, understand the opinions of others, and express this idea competently both orally and in writing. The main role is played by the development of a literate person who thinks independently and has a developed speech culture. Based on the above considerations, it can be said that the comprehensive intellectual development of today's youth and the further enhancement of their talents are a priority issue for the education system. Therefore, in this article, we highlight the importance of the approach to developing talents in students and the characteristics of determining giftedness.

In conclusion, globalization processes are placing new demands and tasks on education. Teaching based on the 4K approach serves as an effective approach that meets these demands. Through this approach, students are formed as creative, critical thinkers, open to communication and ready for cooperation. Therefore, it is advisable for teachers to design lessons based on the principles of the 4K approach in their work. Also, in the era of globalization, education should not be limited to providing knowledge only, but also serve to develop soft skills in students necessary for a successful life in the modern world. The 4K approach is one of the most effective approaches on this path.

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